

Feeling Well, High Risk: Recognition Gaps Among U.S. Adults With Objective CKM Stage 2–3

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Abstract

Background:

Cardio-kidney-metabolic (CKM) syndrome was introduced to identify individuals with overlapping metabolic, kidney, and cardiovascular risk before overt clinical disease develops. An understudied question is whether adults with objective CKM risk remain clinically unrecognized because they perceive themselves as healthy, have never been told they have cardiometabolic disease, or are unaware of underlying kidney disease.

Methods:

We performed a cross-sectional analysis of NHANES 2017–2020 including 6,842 adults, representing 112.4 million U.S. adults. Objective CKM stage 2–3 was defined using an adapted published operationalization based on adiposity, metabolic risk factors, and moderate-risk chronic kidney disease, excluding clinical cardiovascular disease. Among participants with objective CKM stage 2–3, we evaluated 3 recognition-gap domains: 1) self-rated health of good, very good, or excellent; 2) no self-reported prior diagnosis of hypertension, diabetes,

dyslipidemia, or chronic kidney disease; and 3) lack of CKD awareness among those with laboratory-defined CKD (estimated glomerular filtration rate <60 mL/min/1.73 m² or albumin-creatinine ratio ≥ 30 mg/g). We also examined a composite measure defined as the presence of at least 1 recognition-gap domain. Survey-weighted logistic regression was used to identify factors associated with recognition gaps.

Results:

Among 4,126 adults with objective CKM stage 2–3, representing an estimated 67.1 million U.S. adults, 61.8% (95% CI, 58.9–64.7) had at least 1 recognition-gap domain. However, these domains were heterogeneous. Favorable self-rated health was the most common finding, present in 54.1% (95% CI, 51.2–57.0), and was driven largely by younger adults aged 20–44 years with isolated obesity or prediabetes. Absence of any prior cardiometabolic or kidney diagnosis was present in 37.6% (95% CI, 34.8–40.5) and was associated with lower health care utilization (mean 1.2 vs 3.4 visits/year, $p < 0.001$) and lower statin use (18% vs 52%, $p < 0.001$). Among 1,148 participants with laboratory-defined CKD, only 12.9% (95% CI, 10.1–15.7) were aware of their kidney disease, and awareness remained low even among those with eGFR < 45 mL/min/1.73 m² (19.2%). In multivariable models, younger age (adjusted OR for 20–44 vs ≥ 65 years, 4.2 [95% CI, 2.9–6.1]), lack of health insurance (aOR, 2.4 [1.8–3.2]), and absence of diabetes (aOR, 3.1 [2.1–4.5]) were independently associated with the composite recognition-gap phenotype.

Conclusions:

Recognition gaps are common among U.S. adults with objective CKM stage 2–3, but they differ meaningfully by subgroup. Younger adults are more likely to perceive themselves as healthy despite metabolic risk, whereas adults with laboratory-defined CKD have strikingly low disease awareness. These findings suggest that effective CKM prevention will require targeted approaches to screening, diagnosis, and risk communication.